

Assessment of bradykinesia on people with Parkinson's disease through mechanomyography

Pedro Cunha Carneiro
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Federal University of Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-0120-5273

Alice Rueda
Faculty of Engineering and Arch. Sci
Ryerson University
Toronto, Canada
ORCID: 0000-0002-9977-9653

Luiza Maire David Luiz
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Federal University of Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-4630-6692

Teodiano Freire Bastos Filho
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Federal University of Espírito Santo
Vitória, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-1185-2773

Sridhar Krishnan
Faculty of Engineering and Arch. Sci
Ryerson University
Toronto, Canada
ORCID: 0000-0002-4659-564X

Adriano de Oliveira Andrade
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Federal University of Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-5689-6606

Abstract— This paper demonstrated that it is possible to distinguish severity of bradykinesia using muscle vibration information. Muscle vibration information was captured in mechanomyography (MMG) signal using wearable accelerometer sensors. Two groups of 4 Parkinson's subjects, less and more severe groups, had participated in this study. Each participant performed 4 tasks: finger pinching, hand opening and closing, hand pronation and supination, and wrist flexion and extension. PDPack toolbox was used for event detection and signal processing. Hilbert spectrum was estimated from the resultant signal from three axes of the accelerometer to obtained the power spectrum. Instantaneous mean frequency (IMNF) was then calculated for comparison. The results indicate that more severe bradykinesia has lower IMNF. The difference between the two groups is also visible from the Hilbert spectrum plots.

Keywords—mechanomyography, Parkinson's disease, UPDRS.

I. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) was first described in 1817 by the British physician James Parkinson as shaking palsy. It is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder resulting from the central nervous system's (CNS) cell degeneration [1]. PD is the second most common neurodegenerative disease, following the Alzheimer's disease, drastically impacting someone's quality of life. It is said that approximately 1% of the population over 60 years old will develop the disease [2], and, in Brazil, that number is calculated to be approximately 3.3% of people over 65 years old [3].

The standard definition is the death of the dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpC), or depleted dopamine level in the striatum. Even if SNpC is healthy but the striatum is not able to receive dopamine, then the result is the same [4]. As the dopamine neurotransmitter helps control the body's voluntary movements, patients with Parkinson's disease have reduced motor control. The reduced control is reflected in specific signs and symptoms. The new Movement Disorder Society (MDS) diagnostic criteria requires presents of bradykinesia plus one or more of the two cardinal syndromes, tremor and rigidity [5-6].

As the disease progresses, some secondary complications from individual psychosocial factors and from each individual's physical symptoms may arise, such as: poor movements, loss of facial expression spontaneity (masked face), gait disorders, as well as, cardiopulmonary changes [7]. Even though PD's symptoms are very characteristic, its causes are still unknown. Nevertheless, genetic and environmental factors can contribute to the development of the disease [4].

Bradykinesia is one of the main PD symptoms indicating the slowness when performing movements [8], taking patients diagnosed with the disease more time to execute a specific task compared to healthy individuals. Simple day-to-day tasks, such as flipping a book page, tying your shoes, adding up coins, are harder and harder for PD patients to perform due to the movement slowness [9].

The standard scale in the clinical environment is the Movement Disorder Society's (MDS) Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (UPDRS) [10]. The items in the scale can be rated by experts on a scale of 0 to 4 with 0 means normal and 4 means severe. The scales for clinical assessment are said to be relatively subjective, indicating the need and importance of objective measures to aid in the diagnosis and stage of the disease.

A lot of the studies have been showing alternatives on how to quantify bradykinesia and the use of inertial parameters from gyroscopes, accelerometers or magnetometers [11-13]. Thus, extracting features and analyzing parameters acquired through sensors may be useful when assessing bradykinesia, as well as relating it to the UPDRS score.

Mechanomyography (MMG) is a non-invasive technique where electrodes are placed in order to record the vibrations produced by the skeletal muscles during contractions [14]. This technique represents the mechanical activity of a muscle detected from specific transducers which record the surface muscular oscillations associated with the muscular activity from motor units, with a frequency below 50 Hz [15].

The advantages of MMG compared to electromyography (EMG) are related to placement. Unlike EMG signals, MMG sensors do not need to be precisely placed [16]. Also, the MMG signal is a mechanical signal so it is not affected by the

change in the impedance in the skin caused by sweat, or hair [17].

The goal of this work is to investigate the relationship between features extracted from the MMG signal and UPDRS scores for patients diagnosed with Parkinson's disease. Also, features related to characterizing bradykinesia on people with Parkinson's disease and motor standards of healthy individuals will be compared.

This paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the materials and methods used in this work, such as data acquisition, dataset information and signal processing. Section III shows the results obtained after the feature extraction. Section IV presents our discussion and conclusions.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Mechanomyography (MMG) and data acquisition

The data acquisition protocol was done by placing the sensors on the extensor and flexor carpi ulnaris muscles in order to assess parameters to characterize Parkinson's bradykinesia when performing a sequence containing four tasks: finger pinching (Fig 1A), hand opening and closing (Fig 1B), hand pronation and supination (Fig 1C), and wrist flexion and extension (Fig 1D).

Fig. 1. Sequence of tasks performed by the subjects: A - finger pinching; B - hand opening and closing; C - hand pronation and supination; D - wrist flexion and extension, as well as the accelerometers positioning.

In this paper, the TREMSSEN system was used for data acquisition (sampling frequency – 50 Hz), by using two tri-axial accelerometers: one accelerometer (A1) positioned in the arm, and the other accelerometer (A2) in the wrist, as shown in Fig. 1. This protocol was repeated three times for each patient and it was based on tasks that are related to bradykinesia. In this paper, we analyzed only the finger pinch and pronation/supination tasks.

B. Dataset

There were 8 subjects participated in this study. These subjects were grouped into less and more severe groups. Subjects in the less severe group have scores less than or equal to 7. Each subject was evaluated and given an UPDRS-III Motor Examination score, by 3 physiotherapists. Only the items 3.4a, 3.4b, 3.5a, 3.5b, 3.6a and 3.6b from the UPDRS-III were taken into account, since they are the items directly related to bradykinesia assessment. The average of the three scores was used in this study, where this score varies between 0 and 24, the minimum and maximum scores for the six evaluated items, respectively. Table 1 present the subjects information including sex (M – male; F - female), age,

UPDRS score, and group (G1 - low severity (score ≤ 7) and G2 - moderate/higher severity (score > 7)).

TABLE I. SUBJECTS INFORMATION SUMMARY: SEX, AGE, UPDRS SCORE, AND GROUP (G1 - LESS SEVERE, G2 – MORE SEVERE).

Information	Subjects (S)							
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8
Sex	M	M	M	M	M	F	M	M
Age	55	50	69	56	70	56	42	48
UPDRS score	8.3	9.7	3.3	9	17	5.3	4	7
Group	G2	G2	G1	G2	G2	G1	G1	G1

C. Signal processing

Data processing and virtualization were conducted using a PDPack tool¹. PDPack is a statistical analysis tool developed in R by Federal University of Uberlândia (UFU) and Ryerson University. This tool is used to process the signals in order to obtain the MMG based on its characteristics.

The first step of this pre-processing was to import the raw accelerometer signals and to detrend the signal. This means that some aspects (a change in the mean over time) that caused some distortion were removed. This eliminated the low frequency movement. The signal detection and segmentation automatically separate the MMG signal into the four tasks. Only two tasks were used in this study, finger pinching and pronation and supination. At the end of the pre-processing, a resultant vector from the 3-axis was calculated and filtered using a 10 Hz high-pass Butterworth Filter in order to eliminate tremor frequencies (2-6 Hz) that predominated in the MMG signal.

For feature extraction, we applied the empirical mode decomposition (EMD), decomposing the time-series into a set of intrinsic mode functions (IMFs). The instantaneous mean frequency (IMNF) was calculated from the Hilbert Spectrum (HS) $P(t, \omega)$ for each subject since it has been proven to be a relevant feature in clinical practice [18]. The IMNF function [19], estimated from the HS, is calculated by Eq. 1:

$$\text{IMNF}(t) = \frac{\int_0^F \omega P(t, \omega) d\omega}{\int_0^F P(t, \omega) d\omega}, \quad (1)$$

where F is the Nyquist frequency and $P(t, \omega)$ is the time-dependent power spectral density.

The boxplots with the IMNF values for finger pinch and pronation and supination tasks were examined. In addition, the power spectral density was compared using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). Fig 2. summarizes the methodology used in this work.

¹PDPack tool is available at:

(<https://github.com/aoandrade/PDPack.git>)

Fig. 2. Block diagram summarizing the methodology.

III. RESULTS

The mechanomyographic signal extracted from the raw data processing is shown in Fig. 3. This figure only exemplified the signal obtained on the x-axis of one of the accelerometers. This processing was done for each axis of the two accelerometers, calculating the resultant amplitude from the three axes.

Fig. 3. Accelerometer 1 (X axis): Raw signal (in the left) and MMG signal (blue signal in the right) with the four tasks segmented after event detection algorithm.

Note that TRESEM allows data collectors to create pulse signals during the acquisition. If the pulse signals exist before and after each task, the segmentation will not include the undesirable noise before and after the task period, and remote non-task periods within the start/stop pulse pair. The resulting four blocks represents the signals of the four tasks performed.

Figs. 4 and 5 show the Hilbert spectra over time for accelerometer 1 in the hand pronation and supination task, and for accelerometer 2 in the finger pinch task, respectively. There is visual difference in the IMNF value (green hatching) over time when comparing the patient with the less advanced bradykinesia symptom with the patient with the more advanced stage symptom.

Fig. 4. Accelerometer 1 – Pronation and Supination: MMG Signal and the 3D Hilbert Spectrum plot with the IMNF over time.

Fig. 5. Accelerometer 2 – Finger pinch: MMG Signal and the 3D Hilbert Spectrum plot with the IMNF over time.

It is noteworthy to note the differences in the signal plots, the patient with a less severe stage of the disease has higher peaks of IMNF, as well as a sudden variation, indicating a greater vibration of the muscles, and less difficulty to perform the tasks, in comparison with the subject at a more advanced stage of the disease.

Fig. 6 shows the boxplots obtained with the IMNF values for pronation and supination for each of the 8 subjects divided into two groups: on the left, the group containing the four subjects with lower severity according to the UPDRS score, and on the right the group with four subjects with a higher severity. Despite very similar IMNF values between the two groups, it is clear that the subjects in the lower severity group (G1) have higher IMNF values compared to the other group (G2).

Fig. 6. Accelerometer 1 – Pronation and Supination: Boxplots with IMNFs for the two groups (G1 – less severity and G2 - high severity)

The power spectral density plots are shown in Figs. 7 and 8. It is important to analyze the normalized amplitude in the frequency range of MMG between 10-20 Hz.

Accelerometer 1 – Pronation and Supination

Fig. 7. Accelerometer 1 – Pronation and Supination: Power spectral density comparison between the less severe and the more severe subjects.

Accelerometer 1 – Finger pinch

Fig. 8. Accelerometer 1 – Finger pinch: Power spectral density comparison between the less severe and the more severe subjects.

IV. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

A lot of the studies have been done using inertial signals from wearable devices. However, instead of using the inertial signal obtained from the accelerometers for bradykinesia analysis, this paper proposed to use MMG signals extracted from the accelerometers. PDPack was used to performing signal processing including event detection, detrending, artifacts removal, and MMG extraction. Hilbert transform of the resultant amplitude of the MMG signal was used for differential analysis. Using data captured from the 8 subjects, 4 less and 4 more severe subjects, we found that MMG signal can be used to differentiate severity of the group.

We can hypothesize that the higher the bradykinesia symptom in the subject (higher severity), the higher the tremor level, and therefore the lower the vibration of the muscle while performing the task. The Hilbert Spectrum results showed that subjects with lower UPDRS score presented higher frequency peaks and IMNF values compared to the subjects with higher severity. An objective assessment, along with clinical observations, can be crucial in improving the quality of patient care, enabling more personalized care and helping to determine the stage of the Parkinson's disease.

For future studies, we suggest to fine-tune the acquisition protocol: (1) try to avoid or reduce abrupt movements of the subjects during data acquisition, (2) increase the database, and (3) to test robustness of the proposed feature extraction.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would like to thank CAPES and Canada's NSERC for the financial support of this research and "Associação de Parkinson do Triângulo" for the partnership in the work.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. E. Emborg, "Evaluation of animal models of Parkinson's disease for neuroprotective strategies," *J Neurosci Meth*, vol. 139, no. 2, pp. 121-143, 2004.
- [2] F. Sprenger, W. Poewe, "Management of motor and non-motor symptoms in Parkinson's disease," *CNS Drugs*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 259-272, 2013.
- [3] M. T. Barbosa et al., "Parkinsonism and Parkinson's disease in the elderly: a community-based survey in Brazil (the Bambuí study)," *Movement Disorders*, vol. 21, no. 6, pp. 800-808, 2006.
- [4] L. V. Kalia and A. E. Lang, "Parkinson's disease," *Lancet*, vol. 386, no. 9996, pp. 896-912, 2015.
- [5] R. B. Postuma et al., "MDS clinical diagnostic criteria for Parkinson's disease," *Mov. Disord.*, vol. 30, no. 12, pp. 1591-1599, 2015.
- [6] R. B. Postuma et al., "Validation of the MDS clinical diagnostic criteria for Parkinson's disease," *Mov. Disord.*, vol. 33, no. 10, pp. 1601-1608, 2018.
- [7] A. L. S. Barros et al., "Doença de Parkinson: uma visão interdisciplinar," São José dos Campos: Pulso, pp. 19-25, 2006.
- [8] M. E. Morris, "Movement disorders in people with Parkinson disease: a model for physical therapy," *Phy Ther*, vol. 80, no. 6, pp. 578-597, 2000.
- [9] S. B. O'Sullivan, T. J. Schmitz, "Fisioterapia: avaliação e tratamento," In: Fisioterapia: avaliação e tratamento. 2004.
- [10] C. G. Goetz et al., "Movement Disorder Society-sponsored revision of the Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS): scale presentation and clinimetric testing results," *Mov Disord*, vol. 23, no. 15, pp. 2129-2170, 2008.
- [11] O. Martinez-Manzaena et al., "A method for automatic and objective scoring of bradykinesia using orientation sensors and classification algorithms," *IEEE T Biomed Eng*, vol. 63, no. 5, pp. 1016-1024, 2016.
- [12] H. Dai, L. T. D'Angelo, "A portable system for quantitative assessment of parkinsonian bradykinesia during deep-brain stimulation surgery," In: *Advances in Biomedical Engineering (ICABME)*, 2013. [2nd International Conference on. IEEE. pp. 77-80, 2013].
- [13] D. A. Heldman et al., "The modified bradykinesia rating scale for Parkinson's disease: reliability and comparison with kinematic measures," *Movement Disorders*, vol. 26, no. 10, p. 1859-1863, 2011.
- [14] M. A. Vaz, W. Herzog, "A mecanomiografia como técnica não-invasiva para o estudo da função muscular," *Movimento*, vol. 5, no. 10, pp. 15-20, 1999.
- [15] E. Krueger et al., "Advances and perspectives of mechanomyography," *Rev Bras Eng Biomed*, vol. 30, no. 4, pp. 384-401, 2014.
- [16] N. Alves, T. Chau, "Stationarity distributions of mechanomyogram signals from isometric contractions of extrinsic hand muscles during functional grasping," *J Electromy Kines*, vol. 18, no. 3, p. 509-515, 2008.
- [17] H. B. Xie, Y. P. Zheng, J. Y. Guo, "Classification of the mechanomyogram signal using a wavelet packet transform and singular value decomposition for multifunction prosthesis control," *Phys Meas*, vol. 30, no. 5, p. 441, 2009.
- [18] A. O. Andrade, P. Kyberd, S. J. Nasuto, "The application of the Hilbert spectrum to the analysis of electromyographic signals," *Information Sci*, vol. 178, no. 9, p. 2176-2193, 2008.
- [19] J. S. Karlsson, B. Gerdle, M. Akay, "Analyzing surface myoelectric signals recorded during isokinetic contractions," *IEEE Eng Med Biology Magazine*, vol. 20, no. 6, p. 97-105, 2001.